

T. Walther

Comparison of different scanning electron microscopy methods (SEM, WDX, μ XRF) to detect thin In(Ga)As layers deposited on top of GaAs

For very thin surface layers on bulk substrates the interaction volume for X-ray generation in top-down geometry will always dominate so quantification is tricky. A top-down investigation of several thin In(Ga)As layers grown on GaAs (see table 1) is able to detect indium in an InAs layer as thin as an individual unit cell even in a simple Hitachi 3030+ tabletop SEM with 30mm² Bruker XFlash 430 SDD (15kV, 1h acquisition time) [1]. The red curve in Fig. 1 is for ≈ 2 nm InAs equivalent where both In L α and L β lines are clearly visible, the purple for ≈ 1 nm InAs equivalent shows only the stronger In L α line. For ≈ 0.4 nm InAs equivalent (light blue) the In signal of 1110 ± 700 counts is near the detection limit. Quantification of EDX at 5 and 15kV is similar to both wavelength dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (WDXS) in a dedicated electron microprobe at 5kV where beam current is more than an order of magnitude higher, and micro X-ray fluorescence (μ XRF) with Rh cathode at 50kV and an Al filter (Fig. 2), where penetration will be an order of magnitude deeper.

Fig. 1: SEM-EDXS at 15kV of samples ME1064-1066

Fig. 2: μ XRF at 25 and 50kV of sample AF9151 (thanks to Heath Young and Stephan Boehm from Bruker Nano Analytics, Berlin)

sample	nominal thickness [nm]	equivalent InAs MLs	
		nominal	EDXS
ME1065	2nm $\text{In}_{0.2}\text{Ga}_{0.8}\text{As}$	1.4	0.9 ± 0.6
ME1066	5nm $\text{In}_{0.2}\text{Ga}_{0.8}\text{As}$	3.5	5.1 ± 0.7
ME1064	10nm $\text{In}_{0.2}\text{Ga}_{0.8}\text{As}$	7.0	8.6 ± 0.6
AF 9151	0.46nm InAs	1.5	2.7 ± 0.8

Table 1: quantification of SEM-EDXS

Reference:

[1] T. Walther. *Nanomaterials* **12**:13 (2022) 2220